

Dickinson's poetic themes and figurative language

Nathaniel G. Gido¹
Emardy T. Barbecho²
Don Roel G. Arias³
Lorraine R. Dacanay¹
Sarah M. Nemenzo¹

College of Arts and Sciences^{1,2,3}

University of the Visayas, Philippines¹

Cebu Technological University-Carmen Campus, Philippines²

Cebu Academy-Carmen, Philippines³

sarahnemenzo@yahoo.com

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ABSTRACT

The language of poetry is a symbolic imitation that expresses life and describes the world. Studying Emily Dickinson's representative poems is the benchmark of understanding one's self and the world in general. The study analyzes poetic themes and figurative language. It undertakes on the pervading themes and/or visions in the representative poems in their intellectual and emotive dimension; and (2) figurative language in terms of figures of sense and sounds. The study uses the textual analysis of Dickinson's five representative poems as the basis of the thematic content as suggested by Knickerbockers (2005). These poems: (a) I've Ceded - I've Stopped being Theirs; (b) Apparently with No Surprise; (c) Soul Selects Her Own Society; (d) I Know that He Exists; and (e) I Cannot Live Without You are analyzed using intellectual and emotive dimensions. These poetic themes are reinforced by alliteration, personification, rhyme, apostrophe and symbolism, metaphor, simile, assonance and consonance as the figures of speech used. These are then categorized into figurative language as to sense and sound.

Keywords: *figurative language, intellectual and emotive dimensions, model lesson, poetic themes*

I. INTRODUCTION

This study analyzes the poetic themes and figurative language in the representative poems of Emily Dickinson using the literary theories such as theories of mimesis, expressivism, textuality, and literary historicism. It seeks to understand and interpret the pervading themes or visions in the poems in their intellectual and emotive dimensions, the transaction of meaning, as well as the figurative language as to sense and sound.

Poetry is one of the genres of literature which makes the readers feel, see, take delight in the music and meaning, and hence, become part of

the emotion. However, the study of poetry is one of the most difficult and neglected literary genres in the secondary school instruction because of its complicated nature as a literary type that most Language teachers tend to exclude in their instructional content as manifested in the study of Fontanoza (1997) as cited in Knickerbocker (2005). This difficulty is due to a lack of understanding of the integral unity of structure and meaning in poetic form using figurative or symbolic language that a good number of language teachers refuse to explore because of its complexity. With this convention, learners have

learned to distrust the study of poetry because of the blundering source of selections given to them.

Because of the complicated nature of understanding poetry in spite of its beauty, as claimed by studies in the past, it further reveals that the study of poetry is significant to man's life for it uplifts the emotions and the mind as well. However, analyzing poems as a work of art necessitates a thorough understanding of the themes, and the figurative language that helps to crop the meaning or sense and sound of the literary genre. Each reader has the freedom to assess the coherence of the writer's works and interpret it in the light of his or her own experience and attitudes to the world.

In the study, representative poems of Emily Dickinson are selected in order to (1) analyze the pervading poetic themes or visions in terms of: intellectual dimension and emotive dimension; and (2) analyze the figurative language in the poems in terms of sense and sounds.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This literary research assumes that Emily Dickinson's representative poems are multi-dimensional in their poetic themes or visions through the intellectual and emotive dimensions in the transaction of meaning and in their images as to sense and sound. This research assumption is supported by the critical theories of mimesis, expressivism, textuality and historicism.

Theory of Mimesis. The idea of this theory assumes that a literary work is an imitation, a representation, or a copy of whatever it copies, imitates, represents, or signifies: the relation between text and its concealed antecedents. As Aristotle once said, this theory is the most primitive aesthetic theory (Arias, 2012). In this regard, he embraces the concept of the theory of mimesis suggesting that art is an imitation of the exterior world and the actions of people. Thus, mimetic criticism emphasizes the correspondence of the work to external reality, and the context in which the work is studied.

Apparently, mimetic criticism is committed to truth, reality, and the idea that literature, in some ways imitates life. It is this idea that leads the mimetic critic to review the work as a true imitation, reflection, or representation of the

world and human life (Binongo as cited in Arias, 2012).

Theory of Expressivism. The idea of expressivism locates the literary work in the author: what the writer expressed, emphasizing the presence of the artist in the literary work. The literary text is directly considered as an expression of the author's inner being.

Biographical analysis is anchored on the theory of expressivism with the psychology of the author emerging as the subject for investigation. Inquiry into the nature of the poem merges with the inquiry into the nature of the poet. Hence, this theory sees a literary work as a reflection of the author's life and times on the life and times of the characters or personae in the literary work.

Also known as subjective theory, its literary critical perspective holds that certain literary works are better understood by readers if they know something about the author's race, moment and milieu. This theory, moreover, seeks to explain a work by relating to the author's religion, education, political leanings, even his or her sickness.

This literary investigation reflects society's treatment to its people as depicted in the situations of the studied poems. Consequently, it gives a total picture on how the persona works for himself or herself to generate the pervading theme found in every poem (Dreier, 1999).

Theory of Textuality. The idea of textuality holds that a literary text in itself is made up of formalistic elements that determine, in a unified fashion, the meaning or content of the text and that literature follows varied genres including drama for its own specific purpose in conveying meaning (Patterson, 2014).

Specifically, the theory of textuality can either be actualized through: "the work as an entity in itself"; or "the work as a unity of formalistic elements that determine its meaning" (Abrams as cited in Arias, 2012).

Theory of Literary Historicism. Literary Historicism is a theory applied to literature that suggests literature must be studied and interpreted within the context of both the history of the author and the history of the critic. The theory used to examine the text's historical origins, such as: the time, the place in which the text was

written, its sources, the events, dates, persons, places, things, and customs that are mentioned or implied in the text. The theory evaluates how the work is influenced by the time in which it was produced. It examines the social sphere in which the author moved the psychological background of the author, the books and theories, that may have influenced the author, and any other factors which influenced the work of literature (Williams, 2003).

The five selected poems of Emily Dickinson are analyzed using the four theories. The theory of Mimesis is used in the study because the pieces of Dickinson poems are imitation of life. The theory of Expressivism is utilized because the understanding of these poems is attributed to the author's race, religion, education, political learnings and her sickness. The theory of Textuality is emphasized to determine the formalistic elements and its meaning. Lastly, the theory of Historicism is applied to examine the text's historical origins, thus, when the poems were written.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study, concerned with the making of textual interpretation of the poetic themes and figure of speech in the representative poems of Dickinson, uses the textual analysis method of research based on the literary content of the poems or the so called "fact-finding with adequate interpretation" which are done in terms of an appraisal of "available data in printed form" (Pilapil, 1998 as cited in Arias, 2008).

The researchers chose five poems out of two thousand poems of Emily Dickinson as the basis of the thematic content as suggested by Knickerbocker (Evans, 1975) of: (a) self-knowledge and identity; (b) society and self; (c) religious and meta-physical values; (d) love and (e) hate. These five poems written by Emily Dickinson were therefore chosen for analysis: (a) I've Ceded - I've Stopped Being Theirs; (b) Apparently With no Surprise; (c) The Soul Selects Her Own Society; (d) I Know That He Exist; and (e) I Cannot Live With You. This qualitative type of research requires the researcher to correctly interpret the available printed form of literature. Since the study is mainly to identify the poetic

themes and the figures of speech of the poems, statistical treatment and instruments are neither needed nor used in the course of study and in the gathering of data. In solving the sub-problems that comprised the groundwork for the conduct of the study, a multi-dimensional analysis on the use of poetic language and themes was undertaken in order to exhibit a clear-cut comprehensive data interpretation. Likewise, the rudiments of discourse analysis are reviewed and studied.

Analysis of Data. In the study, the dominant themes of the representative poems are analyzed and used. Hence, triangulation method was conducted by the researchers to arrive towards the validity of the study. There were two experts who analyzed and interpreted the five representative poems of Emily Dickinson. The researchers also analyzed the poems using the thematic content. After the three consolidated interpretations, the researchers gathered and compared the results. Whichever interpretation had the most dominant instances of agreement from the experts was considered to be the authentic interpretation of the data. The textual analysis involved the reading through of the poem once to see how much of the author's meaning can be immediately grasped. Then the poem is read the second time, line by line, and the unfamiliar works, concepts, ideas and references are defined. Sometimes, it is helpful to "translate" each line into prose, or simply to substitute simpler words for the more difficult ones. Upon understanding all the basic words and ideas, the poem has to be reread a few more times to pull it all back together, establishing the manner on how themes or poetic visions of the five representative poems under study.

Verbal - Data Generating Procedure

The procedure used in the study is deductive approach which starts with the textuality of poetic themes in terms of intellectual and emotive dimensions, followed by the textuality of figurative language as to sense and sound. The poetic themes revealed in Dickinson's representative poems are analyzed using the approaches of mimesis, expressivism, historicism and textuality. In so doing, we focus on the analysis of the general thought that embodies truth developed in the representative poem.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1

Figure of Speech of the Poem "I've Ceded - I've Stopped Being Theirs"

FIGURES OF SPEECH	TYPE	SAMPLE POETIC LINES
Rhyme	Sound	I've Ceded - I've Stopped Being Theirs - The name they dropped upon my face And They can put it with my Dolls My childhood, and the strings of spools; My second rank - too small at first- Crowned crowning - on my Father's breast But this time - adequate - Erect - With will to choose, or to reject
Alliteration	Sound	The name They dropped upon my face Called to the Full - The - Crescent dropped. Crowned - crowning - on my Father's breast
Assonance	Sound	The name They dropped upon my face
Metaphor	Sense	Existence's whole are filled up with one small diadem.

Poetic Theme in I'm Ceded - I've Stopped Being Theirs

The poetic theme of the poem reveals a transition of self-awareness and identity as its intellectual dimension and a transfiguring experience triggered by dismay towards authority as its emotive dimension.

Intellectual Dimension. The religious climate of her time greatly has influenced Emily Dickinson's life. Her works grapple continuously with concerns of spirituality. One of the aspects of spiritual representation in the poet's works is the use of sacramental imagery.

Mimesis reveals that this poem is an observation of the phenomena of human identity. It is an explication of how humans could think of achieving self - knowledge. It describes the persona's psychological metamorphosis in terms of two baptisms which conferred name and identity: the first, the sacramental baptism in the patriarchal Church, when she was an unknowing and helpless baby; the second a self-baptism, an act of choice and will be undertaken in full consciousness. The speaker disavows her

infant baptism and the identity conferred with it and asserts another baptism enacted by and for herself as revealed in lines 2-4:

*The name they dropped upon my face
With water, in the country church
Is finished, using now...*

The speaker makes it clear that she is done with the water "in the country church" and with other tokens of childhood. Baptized before without a choice, she undergoes a figurative baptism this time "consciousness of grace", in the transformation of identity that appears to have cosmic significance as expressed in the second stanza (lines 8 - 11):

*Baptized before, without choice,
But this time consciously, of Grace -
Unto supremest name -
Called to the Full - The Crescent
dropped -*

The first stanza concludes a powerful visual comment on the unravelling of logic that is extended through the second and countered in the third. The speaker's rejection of the religious rite and its power to name is juxtaposed in this stanza with her rejection of the female socialization process as indicated by the dolls of childhood and the women's work of threading spools. Throughout the second and third stanzas, the issue of choice becomes central to the poem. Denied choice in the original baptism, she is now asserting her own power and right to choose. This is a poem of great pride—not pridefulness, but self-confirmation. It is a poem of movement from childhood to womanhood, of transcending the patriarchal condition of bearing her father's name and crowning—"on my Father's breast" (line 15). The speaker is now a conscious Queen (from being a half unconscious Queen) "Adequate-Erect" (lines 16 - 17) and "with will to choose, or to reject" (line 18).

Historicism reveals that Emily's father, one of the wealthiest and most respected citizens of the town, was a leader of the church and a zealous defender of its orthodoxy against the current "New thought" emanating from Concord or where

Emerson was formulating his Transcendentalism doctrines—a belief in the superiority of the intuitive to sensory knowledge. “Squire Dickinson, as he was often called, saw to it that his family attended Sunday meetings, but he was unable to protect Emily from the latest infidelity, “transcendentalism “ for Ben Newton, a law student in his office gave Emerson’s poems to her for Christmas. Thereafter, she had two “fathers”: Edward Dickinson, to whom she was tied by the strongest bonds of love and gratitude, and Ralph Waldo Emerson, her intellectual validator, who assured her that her religious doubts were not unreasonable and who inspired her to pursue religious intuitions that could not be fitted into Amherst orthodoxy.

Emotive Dimension. The poem describes a transfiguring experience. The speaker tells of her dismay at having been named and baptized without knowledge that she was subscribing to an external authority when a child and now as an adult, in underscoring a simplistic belief that she can correct the error of her earlier state of “unconsciousness”. Engaging the reader’s desire to agreeably act and leading the reader to consent to the speaker’s “insistence” is a new baptism, this time “consciously, of Grace “(line 9). Clearly here the reader sees what the poet wishes him or her to see with a new closeness and clarity.

Because the readers hear the speaker retroactively recall an authority she surrendered unknowingly, they can hear the voice of that earlier authority in her present determination. Readers take note of the role that “They” play in this poem. It becomes clear that “They” are her own family members. “They” are the ones who named her and had control over things of her childhood. Even if readers can deduce that “They” represent the people who would have the most immediate control over her life, the ambiguity of the pronoun serves a further purpose. “They” is often used to represent the power structures of society itself. “They” are the legislators of life, the unseen yet fully felt powers that institute an oppressive ideology. The readers can see more than the speaker. They see the three systems of social control mutually supportive and interactive—the power of naming, the dogma of traditional Christianity, and the social construction of “femininity”.

Dickinson was a great prolific letter writer - her letters reveal a slow transformation of style during her early 20’s from conventionally phrased, well wrought sentences to spare, gnomic highly charged and often difficult phrasings punctuated by dashes and with capitalizations for emphasis. This style is also in her short poems, often obscure, deceptively simple. The poems through this style of writing using dashes and sporadic capitalizations of nouns have a way of focusing the reader’s attention to where one proceeds word by word, savouring the audacity and rightness of each choice of word.

This poem partakes of the sense of being “twice born” or in Christian liturgy, confirmed. Baptism in New England Puritan churches and their successors served as a child’s introduction to the community and seal of God’s covenant. It indicated the community’s expectation that God intended the child’s salvation. The baptized child and the young adult could then pursue salvation. The speaker in this poem effectively projects her experience of a narrow “crescent” or empty “Arc” rather than a complete circle of faith. Now as an adult, she rejects the identity imposed on her by other people choices; the dolls she mentioned that were given to her, or the fancy needlework (strings of spools) (lines 5 - 6). The speaker makes it clear that she has not matured into a stereotyped woman she assumes her family and society had anticipated and rejects her baptismal identity as a sign of those false expectations.

Emily Dickinson’s biography tells that when she was fifteen, she shocked her pious classmate at Mount Holy Yoke Female Seminary by refusing to confess her belief in God during an evangelical prayer meeting. Such a refusal required an astonishing degree of courage. Her poems and letters indicated that throughout her life she felt she had a direct route to the Infinite especially through the world of the mind and the Churches, sermons, preachers, revival meetings and theological vocabulary did express her sense of eternity. This exemplifies what Croghan (2007) posits “In explaining and/or questioning human experiences, writers are never alone.” The word table below illustrates the figures of speech of the sample poetic lines.

Table 2
Figure of Speech of the Poem "Apparently With No Surprise"

FIGURES OF SPEECH	TYPE	SAMPLE POETIC LINES
Symbolism	Sense	To any happy flower The frost beheads it at its play The sun proceeds unmoved To measure off another day For an approving God
Assonance	Sound	The frost beheads <i>it</i> at its play. <i>In</i> accidental power.
Augmentation	Sound	The blond assassin <i>passes</i> on, The sun <i>proceeds</i> unmoved
Rhyme	Sound	To any happy flower The frost beheads it at its play In accidental power

Poetic Theme in Apparently With No Surprise

"Apparently With No Surprise" has for its poetic theme a contrast between joyful innocence and fearful destruction as it intellectual dimension and grim, savage timbre created by the horrific picture of death as the emotive dimension.

Intellectual Dimension. The poem makes a contrast between joyful innocence (happy flower... at its play) (lines 2 - 3) and fearful destruction (frost...beheads it) (line 3). And the cause of destruction - "the blond assassin" (line 5) is specially identified. The assassin (whose connotation is terror and violence) is described as not dark but "blond" or white, connoting innocence and beauty. This destructive agent in other words is among the most exquisite creation of God's handiworks. The poet is then shocked by what has happened which seems inconsistent with the role of benevolence in the universe. In an ironic reference to an approving God (line 8), the poet raises a query on whether or not the forces that created and govern the universe actually are benevolent, making the reader think that the poet is unduly disturbed over the death of the flower. The intellectual sense in the first stanza of "happy flower", "at its play" and the "frost...beheading it" creates a situation where the reader is made to see someone killing another while the latter is "at play". The second stanza recalls how nothing in nature or no one around that someone who was killed seemed to care. Although the picture that is painted by these images is horrifying, the

persona sounds like she too is unduly disturbed over the death of that flower. That she even made reference to an approving God is relenting to God's will that death comes to people without prior or due notice and that the "assassin" is another of God's handiworks, is innocent for it gets its accidental power as fate. This, the persona in effect, persuades the listener to accept. The poem concludes with a motion that what is true for the flower is true throughout nature. Death, even early or accidental—in terrible juxtaposition with beauty—is its (nature's) constant condition: the fate that befalls the flower within us. Death is the end of the process.

Emotive Dimension. Intoned with a grim, almost savage timbre, the winter successfully creates a horrific picture of death being a constant condition of nature. What makes the killing (the frost beheads the flower...) horrible is that nothing else in nature is disturbed by it or seems even to notice it, as seen in lines 6-7:

*The sun proceeds unmoved
To measure off another day*

Nothing in nature stops and pauses. The flower itself is not surprised. And even God—the one who we have been told is benevolent and concerned over the least sparrow's fall—seems to approve of what has happened. For He shows no displeasure and He supposedly created the frost as well as the flower. The compact two—stanza poem expresses a feeling that persuades the reader of the persona's cold and matter-of-fact assent of the flower's beheading which unusually corresponds to the flower's response to its beheading and God's ready acceptance of it. The impact of this emotion persuades the reader to consider and ponder over the fate that befell the flower. The words "any" (line 2) and "play" (line 3) in the first three lines of the poem imply a comparison between the flower and humans, thus, engaging the reader to raise a dreadful question—if the destructive agent of this world is among the most exquisite creations of God, isn't death inconsistent with the benevolence of the universe? In answer to this raised question, we see an implied criticism of human thinking in the poem. This exemplifies Spender's (2007) "awareness of the unfamiliar"—the smallest of

man in relation to the vastness of the universe, the unknown. The word table below illustrates the figures of speech of the sample poetic lines.

Table 3
Figure of Speech of the Poem "The Soul Selects Her Own Society"

FIGURES OF SPEECH	TYPE	SAMPLE POETIC LINES
Alliteration	Sound	The <u>S</u> oul <u>S</u> elects Her Own <u>S</u> ociety
Rhyme	Sound	The Soul Selects Her Own Society The shuts the Door On Her Divine majority Obtrude no more
Metaphor	Sound	... Then shuts the Door At her low gate
Simile	Sense	Then close the valves of her attention Like stone

Poetic Theme in The Soul Selects Her Own Society

This poem has a poetic theme of a tribute to the power and sanctity of the private self as intellectual dimension and a feeling of solitude evoked by the choice of isolation as emotive dimension.

Intellectual Dimension. The poet here pays tribute to the power and sanctity of the private self. The poet declares that the persona is not at home to all others. The individual self (the soul) selects the people he or she allows intimacy with and then "shuts the door" (lines 1-2), keeping all out but her selected ones, "divine majority" (line 3) no matter how few. The soul is shown living within a space defined by a door, gate, and mat. The external world, with its nations and their rulers, is kept outside. The poet further reveals that the persona would not even respond to an emperor begging for her company though chariots may bring them as lines 9 - 2 intones:

*I've known her from an ample nation
Choose one
Then close the valves of her attention
Like stone.*

The poet suggests that the persona is "longing for one" with whom to share the privacy,

providing the reader with a "reflection of one's inner self" as Rozakis (2010) aptly puts it. For women of Dickinson's class, the appropriate social institutions were the family and the church: with these came many societal obligations. Women of her day were not expected to be intellectuals, leaders, thinkers.

Emily Dickinson was a woman who created her own avenue of thought, refusing those offered by church and society. The poem describes the persona's choice of isolating herself from a social group. The imagery of the house the use of the domestic vocabulary door, low gate and mat asserts the persona's indifference to the outside world. The enclosed space of the soul's (the persona's) house, established not as a grand palace but rather a simple house, is more than adequate for a queenly life and ambassadors or emperors (kneeling down upon her mat...) of the external world's glories can easily be scorned. This intellectual house imagery is reinforced by the valves seen as doors permitting entry from outside or separating soul from world. A look into the life of the poet under study, Emily Dickinson reveals that in the remaining years of her life, there marked a gradual retreat from society. Though she reflected her community's Protestants and Calvinistic frame of reference, religious terminology in her poetry does not indicate the she held orthodox religious belief. She is by turn satirical, sceptical, awed, reverent, speculative, ironic or god-like herself.

Emotive Dimension. The poem effectively invokes the feeling of solitude. The persona has explicitly expressed her desire not to avail herself of a social life, concealing her mind, like her person, from all but a very few chosen friends (divine majority) (line 3). The poem also implies how isolation is confinement. When the soul turns in upon her own concerns, she closes "the valves of her attention-/like stone". Valves permit the flow of whatever they regulate in one direction only: here, from outside to inside, while their association with the stone makes the walls separating soul from the world solid. The persona in the poem is strongly declaring her instinctive preferences and choices without regard to rank or personal advantages. She is someone defiantly non-rational making allegiances only to the self

and a few others—persuading the addressee of the persona’s private and guarded revelation of committing herself only to a few, leading the reader to react agreeably to it, engaging the listener’s desires of understanding the persona’s emotional state of life. This “sharpens”, as Knickerbocker (2005) stresses, the “emotional impact on the reader”. The word table below illustrates the figures of speech of the sample poetic lines.

Table 4
Figure of Speech of the Poem “I know That He Exists”

FIGURES OF SPEECH	TYPE	SAMPLE POETIC LINES
Alliteration	Sound	Somewhere in s ilence In death’s s tiff s tare H e h as h id rare life Should the g lee g laze
Rhyme	Sound	He has hid his rare life In death’s stiff stare
Personification	Sound	Would not the jest Have crawled too far!
Apostrophe	Sense	Should the glee glaze In death’s stiff stare,
Symbolism	Sense	Should the glee glaze In death’s stiff stare,

Poetic Theme in I Know That He Exists

“I Know That He Exists” reveals for its poetic theme an expression of confident faith—an analysis of the mystery of God as the intellectual dimension and a sense of disturbance or panic as the emotive dimension.

Intellectual Dimension. The poem begins with a simple declarative statement, “I know that He exists,” an expression of confident faith that appears to be gradually and thoroughly undermined by the rest of the poem. Immediately after that initial straightforward statement, the speaker’s lack of concrete knowledge seems to come into view. Doubt may have crept into the speaker’s voice, but this is faith in spite of ... as the title suggests. The readers come to see the speaker’s view that man is denied final knowledge of the Godhead. As the second statement states,

the reader can neither see nor hear God (line 2). He is both hidden “in silence” and “away” from our gross eyes (line 4). Emily Dickinson’s poetry is her response to her experience. To understand her, it is necessary to be familiar with her spiritual belief. The Dickinsons were considered “a representative family of Puritanism”. Aware of the disparity between her own conviction and beliefs and those of her father’s, Emily Dickinson refused to accept her father’s views. The second stanza begins by declaring that life is an instant play. The word “play” here tells that life is a game that which last only an instant. The idea of our God as a “fond ambush” (line 6), in which He will jump out in playful “surprise” after this life is over. At this time, the speaker is happily confident that “Bliss”, the presence of heaven, will be set before him or her. The surprise will be the excitement of finally coming face-to-face with Him. The change from the tone of confident faith in the first two stanza is marked by the single, doubt-filled word “but” (line 9). In the face of the reality of death, all the speaker’s doubts begin to come to the fore. The last two lines of the third stanza condenses the speaker’s mounting the fear of death. This fear leads to the desperate declarations of the final stanza:

*Should the glee glaze
In death’s stiff stare,*

The speaker fears that Death may not be so benevolent after all. The word “jest” (line 15) makes it clear that with or without faith there is a perpetrator behind this life. Someone is responsible for this ambiguous ambush, whether it is He or death. The fear that fills this final stanza is based on that uncertainty. The notion that death may not be quite what it seems to the person who holds a firm faith in the unverifiable begins to surface as the speaker shows a great sense of fear, that all this “play” (life) may be nothing less than tragic and “piercing earnest”.

Emotive Dimension. The words of the final stanza are structured as though they should be expressed as questions, yet the reader should feel a sense of disturbance when finding exclamation points in the place of question marks:

*Would not the fun
Look too expensive!
Would not the jest
Have crawled too far!*

The persona struggled with these questions and concluded that human beings could never achieve a full understanding of God, that behind the covenant and behind the Scriptures there looms an inconceivable being about whom no man could confidently predict anything. The speaker is not asking the reader's opinion on this subject—the speaker is conveying an awful sense of the idea that we are not immortal. The poem ends with an admission that man's ascertainment of God's purpose is clearly limited, giving the reader a sense of fear that this playful fun that we have here on earth would not be worthwhile if we have to confront a merciless glare from death. The earlier sense of life as a game full of fun with a guaranteed happy ending is abandoned. Life now appears frightening. The play has turned mean; the surprise is now meant to scare. In the presence of death, the whole idea of faith has come to seem to be nothing more than a cruel hoax. The feeling is that death is the punch line to a bad joke that has gone "too far". By taking the role of a confused child, the poet adds an extra touch of terror to an old theological question about the mystery of God. The impact of this confusion is the transfer of this apparent fear of death that the persona is sensing to the reader leading into that heightened desperate declaration of the final stanza what the reader should feel a sense of disturbance revealing what Dacillo (1996) considers "as authentic to life and life's realities." Unable to accept the teachings of the Unitarian Church of her family, Emily Dickinson remained agnostic throughout her life—believing that the existence of God is unknown or unknowable despite her desire to experience a religious awakening. This is what Croghan (2007) meant by "an intense realization of a human experience where one may recognize, explain and/or question one's own experiences." This is exemplified in the following word table.

Table 5
Figure of Speech of the Poem "I Cannot Live With You"

FIGURES OF SPEECH	TYPE	SAMPLE POETIC LINES
Rhyme	Sound	On my homesick eye, -- Except that you, than He Shine closer by Though my name Rang loudest On the Heavenly fame
Consonance	Sound	Glow plain – and foreign
Assonance	Sound	Would put out Jesus
Simile	Sense	Our life his porcelain Like a cup
Paradox	Sense	I cannot live with you It would be life
Personification	Sense	Our life his porcelain Like a cup

Poetic Theme in I Cannot Live With You

The poem has for its poetic themes a negation of the possibility of a union between a loved one (its intellectual dimension) and a feeling of hopelessness, desperation and discouragement (its emotive dimension).

Intellectual Dimension. The poem holds a three part argument against a union (I Cannot live with you, die with you or share the Resurrection with you, as either one of the damned or the saved). The poem begins with the persona saying that she cannot live with her loved one because their life together is an object that can only be opened with a key. The sexton, or church officer in charge of the maintenance of the church property, keeps the key. The poem probably refers to Rev. Charles Wadsworth, a Philadelphia clergyman whom the poet in study, Emily Dickinson, met on her way home from a visit to her father in Washington. A look further in the biography of the poet, reveals that Rev. Wadsworth was leaving Amherst for a new post. He accepted a call to move to a church in San Francisco. The Reverend's involvement with God ("you serve heaven ...") (line 30) and with a woman at the same time, the poet is trying to say, is like a porcelain cup that is easily broken. Life is personified as this old cup which is valuable until

a new, better one is available. By using sensory images, the poet develops an interest for the reader and a way of showing what the persona feels. The sense of touch is used when the poet says that one who is dead is frozen. It tells the readers that the persona knows that death isn't a pleasant experience, as expressed in line 17-20:

*And I, could I stand by
And see you freeze,
Without my right of frost?
Death's privilege?*

The persona exclaims that she cannot die with her loved one, for there must always be someone to shut the other's eye or see the loved one die without dying also, as shown in stanza 4 (lines 13 - 16):

*I could not die with you
For one must wait
To shut the other's gaze down -
You could not*

The persona could not rise with her loved one if he will be punished by Jesus for his action, as the persona exclaims that she believes in the promise of salvation. Stanza 6 (lines 21 - 24) expressed:

*Nor could I rise with you,
Because your face
Would put out Jesus
That new grace*

The poet also mentions that the loved one (this man) is now her paradise and what she saw previously only sordid excellence. Indeed there is something blasphemous about a love so total it outshines divinity.

The persona fears that because he deserves heaven, she might be condemned and he saved. She could be saved but he condemned. Either way it would be hell to her if they were apart; lines 41-44 of the 11th stanza expressed:

*And were you - saved
And I - Condemned to be
Where you were not -
That self - were Hell to me -*

At the outset, the persona compares their separation to a door that is slightly open so that there is a possibility they can overcome their differences. The two are such opposites that they "meet apart" with just the "door ajar" (lines 45-47). Then she says that they are separated by oceans. Again, there is the possibility that they can be together if they cross the water barrier. That there's only hope through prayer that they will someday meet again in heaven. The final statement suggests that bleak sustenance is all that supports life. The long checklist of possibilities finally narrows to a harrowing death-in-life. The speaker here doesn't take the conventional path of renouncing earthly love in favour or a more compelling divine love. She refuses it because it is the more powerful of the two.

Emotive Dimension. The mood of the poem is one of hopelessness, desperation and discouragement. In the first stanza of the poem, the readers see the persona denying her inner self. She is saying that she cannot allow herself to have a normal relationship with another individual. She cannot pretend that her life is normal because her life is "behind the shelf" (lines 1-4):

*I cannot live with you
It would be life,
And life is over there
Behind the shelf*

Arguing with herself, the persona advances a catalogue of reasons for her covenant with despair, convinced that her union with the loved one is impossible. She repeats the phrase or idea of "I cannot ... with you and I could not ... with you". Each time she uses the statement, the reader creates an emotion about the beginning of a major resolution. The poem registers the desire for fulfilment each time asserts the inevitability of disappoint. Each stanza contains four lines except for the last line which has six. This is because it is the conclusion of her thought where she states that she will live in despair and depress. The word table on the next page illustrates the figures of speech of the sample poetic lines.

Figurative language, in the general sense, is usually like a picture. Poems depend mainly upon the creation of pictures in the minds, helping the

readers to see things fresh and new. Poets are skillful in their written works to emphasize vivid impressions and to express their imaginative minds. The table below reveals the varied figures of sense and sounds used in the representative poems of Emily Dickinson. Poets are in love with words. The gift of language makes people human, and poets make the fullest use of it. Poetry mobilizes the image—making capacity of language, which delights the ear and stirs the emotions. Emily Dickinson makes a word play of this figurative language in the representative poems under study. Among others, the figures of sense and sounds that are reflected in the poems are as follow: “I’ve Ceded—I’ve Stopped Being Theirs” contains rhyme, alliteration, assonance and metaphor. The poem “Apparently With No Surprise” is played up by the use of symbolism, assonance, augmentation and rhyme. Alliteration, rhyme, metaphor and simile are the figures of speech found in the poem, “The Soul Selects Her Own Society”. “I Know That He Exists” has alliteration, rhyme, personification, apostrophe and symbolism. The figures of speech found in the poem, “I Cannot Live With You” includes rhyme, consonance, assonance, simile, paradox and personification.

V. SUMMARY

The findings are presented according to the sequence of the sub-problems.

The poetic themes are as follows:

(a) Self Knowledge and Identity - The poem under this thematic category, “I’ve Ceded I’ve Stopped Being Theirs” shows a struggle to maintain personal identity as intellectual dimensions and resistance against authority as emotive dimension;

(b) Nature and Self - the poem under this thematic category, “Apparently With No Surprise” shows death being a constant condition of nature as intellectual content and the experience of a profound affliction over death as emotive dimension;

(c) Society and Self - the poem with this thematic content, “The Soul Selects Her Own Society” reveals a deliberate choice to remain private as intellectual dimension and a feeling of solitude evoked by the choice of isolation as

emotive dimension;

(d) Religious and Metaphysical Values - the poem with this thematic content, “I Know That He Exists”, shows an expression of confident faith—an analysis of the mystery of God as intellectual dimension and a sense of bewilderment caused by uncertainty as emotive content;

(e) Love and Hate - the poem with this thematic content, “I Cannot Live With You”, show an ardent desire to be with a loved one and a negation of a possible union as intellectual dimension and hopelessness, desperation, and discouragement as emotive dimension.

The figurative language of the five representative poems reflect the following figurative language used by Emily Dickinson. In her poems, Dickinson uses the figures of sense such as metaphor, symbolism, augmentation, simile, personification, apostrophe and paradox. On the other hand, the figures of sound that can be gleaned from the representative poems are rhyme, alliteration, assonance and consonance. Metaphor surfaces as the most dominant figure of sense and rhyme as the most dominant figure of sound in the poems studied.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis and findings of the study, the following conclusion arrived at: These poetic themes are revealed through the theories of textuality, expressivism, mimesis and historicism. The poetry of Emily Dickinson reveals very personal images and symbols; hence, there is a need to be familiar with her life for it has some bearing on her poems.

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